

DIFFERENCES OF CONVERSATIONAL FEATURES. POLITENESS
AND HESITATION.

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Abstract: Children are taught to communicate from a young age, first in the family, and then in educational institutions. One of the ways to teach communication is the formation of communication skills in the form of training. In kindergarten, the teacher teaches the child to communicate by conducting various activities. First, basic manners, how to talk to adults, how to say hello, how to express gratitude are included. During school age and later, a person is taught to communicate through socio-psychological training. This article provides information on Differences of conversational features, Politeness and hesitation.

Key words: Conversation types, extraversion, introversion, information exchange, team environment.

It is necessary for the person himself to react positively to these methods and take active action. Because a person cannot fully develop both as a subject of activity and as an individual person without communication. A.A. According to Bodalyev, the child communicates even during play. The basis of the educational process is the issue of teaching communication. In the process of labor education, people always feel the need for communication. The educational value of communication is that it expands a person's worldview and develops his psyche. That is, all mental processes are formed through communication. The second direction in the formation of the team environment is the formation of the spiritual culture of team members. For this purpose, it is necessary to provide students with information that stimulates their judgments about human communication, human personality, characteristics of mutual evaluation ("I and others", "I manage through the eyes"). It can be organized through essays, conversations, trainings. Including training in communication methods through special exercises. It is important to start training in spiritual culture from the teenage years, because a strong need for information about one's personality arises at the same time. In adolescence, conflicting experiences about his "I" begin. Information about the human personality and interpersonal communication is necessary at an age when thinking about one's own mental state is intensified, communication is very important and very selective. N.P. According to Anikayeva, each person occupies a certain social role in communication with other people. Roles can fully reveal a person's nature or mask it. But choosing a position or a role will

definitely depend on a person's essence, his strength, weakness, level of potential, self-criticism, thoroughness of his behavior, ability to see himself from the outside.

Sometimes failures in communication force young people to hide and destroy their best qualities in order to be more perfect and protected. During early adolescence, boys and girls experience loneliness. They don't tell anyone about their feelings. Information about oneself and the surrounding people determines communication methods and the desire to organize meaningful communication. For this, it is necessary to have certain spiritual information. Mental characteristics unique to each person are determined by the type of nervous system and, first of all, in temperament: in the rate of exposure, in natural signals (sound, light, color, smell, temperature changes), in social signals (word, event, hypersensitivity, emotional excitability, level of anxiety, extraversion, introversion). Extroversion and introversion are clearly manifested in the field of communication as a mental description of a person. Extroversion is an individual's view of the outside world, and introversion is the view of the inner world. People with dominant extroversion characteristics associated with a strong type of nervous activity tend to be more approachable and open to relationships and acquaintances. They eagerly make new acquaintances, like noisy circles. Introverts are people of weak type of nervous activity. They tend to indulge in their inner world, experiences. They are very concerned about others, they prefer a narrow approach. People in the middle of the "extroversion-introversion" axis are called centroverts in psychology. They are moderately approachable and moderately lonely.

Communication can also be taught by working with speech. For example, training such as reciting a poem out loud, telling a story, also helps in the formation of communication. It is easy to teach preschool children to communicate during play activities. It is important to include game and non-game forms in teaching communication: 1. Introduction of informal communication elements into the lesson. At the same time, the use of didactic games. In them, the role of dialogue organizer is played by one of the students, not the teacher. 2. Focus on the positive aspects of the answer. Students are specially trained to objectively evaluate the answers of their peers, while paying attention to the smallest detail, learning to highlight the most successful aspects of their peers' answers. Arguing how to overcome a flaw, influencing one student to tell the flaw to himself. 3. Social relations between people have their own characteristics in the East. This study guide will help to understand the psychological nature of the changes occurring in the human spirituality and psyche during the renewal of the society. Enriching the spiritual world of young students,

inculcating the foundations of the national idea in their minds, cultivating a sense of patriotism, thinking about the past and the great future, feeling proud of it, conflicts in the process of forming a new way of thinking and their in-depth coverage of elimination problems is required. Communication is a multifaceted process of development of communication between people, born on the basis of cooperative activities and needs. Communication includes the exchange of information between the participants of cooperative activities, which is expressed in the communicative form of communication. People use language as a means of communication when interacting with each other. The second aspect of communication is the interaction of participants. In this, not only words are exchanged, but also actions and situations. For example, it is possible to enter into a transaction between a seller and a buyer without saying a word. The third aspect of communication is the perception of each other. It is important for the participants to understand each other correctly. Thus, three conditional aspects of communication can be distinguished: communicative (giving information), interactive (interaction) and perceptive (mutual perception). The unity of these three aspects of communication is manifested as a way of organizing the interaction and cooperative activity of the interlocutor. The content of communication is the exchange of information, the teacher's use of various communication tools to establish mutual understanding and interaction with students. Educational and didactic tasks of pedagogues cannot be carried out without ensuring the relationship between the teacher and the student community.

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